

FEATURES OF COMPLEX THERAPY IN THE TREATMENT OF PERIODONTAL PATHOLOGY

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Annotation: Inflammatory periodontal diseases, in particular gingivitis and periodontitis, are diseases known to mankind since ancient times. With the progress of civilization, the prevalence of these diseases has increased significantly and acquired general medical as well as social significance. Currently, the facts indicate that systemic processes play one of the most important roles in the pathogenesis of chronic inflammatory periodontal diseases.

Key words: periodontium, somatic pathology.

A modern view on the etiology of chronic inflammatory periodontal diseases considers inflammation of the periodontal tissues not only as a consequence of the impact of the bacterial flora of dental plaque, but also as the body's reaction to the impact of microbial infection located on the teeth and in the subgingival space.

Purpose of the study: to analyze the quality of medical and preventive care for patients with periodontal pathology against the background of general somatic pathology and the development of therapeutic assistanc. Materials and methods

To analyze the quality of treatment and preventive care for patients with periodontal disease and general somatic pathology in city dental clinics, 400 dental medical records of patients aged 16 to 70 years were reviewed, and data from patients in the TMA clinic were analyzed. The structure of somatic diseases was assessed. Analysis of concomitant pathologies in the TMA clinic was carried out if the patient had consent to the processing of personal data. The following parameters were assessed: frequency of dental plaque removal, prescription of remineralizing therapy, availability of high-quality antibacterial and anti-inflammatory drugs, physiotherapeutic treatment. We monitored the quality of advisory care for patients with somatic pathology: we determined the frequency of oral hygiene training, as well as referrals to related specialists and specialists in somatic diseases. Surgical treatment was analyzed: the use of patchwork operations and various types of curettage. The number of patient visits with a specific periodontal diagnosis was assessed.

Results and discussion

The antibacterial and anti-inflammatory treatment carried out was also not provided in full: for pathologies of the cardiovascular system $65.9 \pm 0.7\%$, for diseases of the gastrointestinal tract $70.1 \pm 0.59\%$, for pathologies of the respiratory system $71.7 \pm 0.6\%$, for endocrine disorders $5.7 \pm 0.39\%$, with other forms – $58.1 \pm 0.35\%$. Physiotherapeutic treatment for respiratory pathologies is $9.11 \pm 0.18\%$, which is almost 2 times less than for other diseases we have identified. For pathologies of the cardiovascular system, the figure was $17.1 \pm 0.19\%$, for diseases of the gastrointestinal tract $18.3 \pm 0.19\%$, for endocrine disorders $18.77 \pm 0.19\%$, for other forms - $12, 6 \pm 0.19\%$. $5.7 \pm 0.39\%$, with other forms – $58.1 \pm 0.35\%$. Physiotherapeutic treatment for respiratory

Conclusion

Thus, timely diagnosis of somatic pathology is of paramount importance when choosing the optimal treatment method. Unfortunately, the scope of examinations in outpatient dentistry cannot correspond to the conditions of a hospital or general somatic clinic.

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